

L U M I AI Factory

LUMI AI Factory Service Center
Empowering Europe's AI Ecosystem

D4.4

Containerized workflows

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

The LUMI AI Factory Service Center is funded jointly by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking under Grant Agreement 101234208 and the Participating States FI, CZ, DK, EE, NO, PL.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Title	LUMI AI Factory Service Center
Project Acronym	LUMI-AIF
Project Number	101234208
Type of Action	HORIZON-JU-RIA
Topic	HORIZON-JU-EUROHPC-2025-AI-01-IBA-01
Starting Date of Project	01.03.2025
Ending Date of Project	29.02.2028
Duration of the Project	36 months
Website	lumi-ai-factory.eu

Work Package	WP ₄
Task	T _{4.2} . Provision of rich selection of ready-to-use AI tools
Lead Authors	Ville Ahlgren (CSC)
Contributors	Juha Hulkkonen (CSC) Tomáš Martinovic (IT _{4I}) Pauliina Somekoski (CSC)
Peer Reviewers	Markus Koskela (CSC)
Version	1.0.
Due Date	29.8.2025
Submission Date	29.8.2025

Dissemination level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEN: Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

The LUMI AI Factory Service Center is funded jointly by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking under Grant Agreement 101234208 and the Participating States FI, CZ, DK, EE, NO, PL.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	5.6.2025	Pauliina Somerkoski Ville Ahlgren	Initial version
0.2	24.7.2025	Ville Ahlgren	Added bulk of the document's content and structure.
0.3	25.7.2025	Juha Hulkkonen	Added descriptions for terms.
0.4	4.8.2025	Ville Ahlgren	Overall polish, finalize chapters <i>Next Steps</i> and <i>Workflow Files</i> , and add chapter <i>AI Models, Software, and Use</i> .
0.5	5.8.2025	Ville Ahlgren	Minor grammatical fixes and restructuring the <i>Workflow Catalog</i> chapter.
0.6	12.8.2025	Ville Ahlgren	Added references and improved several sections based on feedback.
0.7	13.8.2025	Tomáš Martinovic	Added clarifying sentence to section <i>Workflows, Containerized</i> and a couple of examples to Vision-Language workflow description.
0.8	18.8.2025	Ville Ahlgren	Minor updates to multiple chapters based on received feedback.
0.9	27.8.2025	Ville Ahlgren	Changed dissemination level to public, final version ready for submission.
1.0	29.8.2025	Anna Luoma	Final quality check performed by the PMO, sent to official review.

Glossary of Terms

Item	Description
Aitta	AI Inference service developed by CSC.
Airflow	Data-engineering oriented workflow engine.
AWQ	Activation Aware Quantization is an AI model compression technique, designed to enable efficient inference while maintaining accuracy.
Docker	Docker is a platform to package software environments into units called containers.
CI/CD	CI Continuous Integration and CD Continuous Delivery are practices in which code changes are automatically tested, integrated, and delivered.
Flash Attention	An efficient algorithm used in large language models to optimize memory access.
GPQA	Graduate-Level Google-Proof Questions and Answers is a benchmark designed to evaluate the reasoning and problem-solving abilities of large language models.
HPC-API	High-Performance Computing - Application Programming Interface.
Llama	A family of large language models developed by Meta AI.
LLM	Large Language Model.
LUST	LUMI User Support Team, responsible for the official LUMI software stack and user support.
Lustre	Lustre is a high-performance distributed file system, commonly used in large-scale computing environments, such as HPC clusters.
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations is a set of practices that aims to streamline the development, deployment, and maintenance of machine learning models
MI250x	AMD GPU designed for high-performance computing and AI workloads, used in systems like LUMI.
MMLU	Massive Multitask Language Understanding is a benchmark for evaluating the multitask accuracy and general knowledge of large language models.
Mistral	Mistral is a family of large language models developed by the company Mistral AI.
Kubeflow	A popular workflow system for machine learning operations
Podman	An open-source container management tool alternative to Docker.
PyTorch	PyTorch is an open-source machine learning library developed by Meta AI, widely used for developing deep learning models.
Qwen	Qwen is a family of large language models developed by Alibaba Cloud.
ROCm	AMD's open source software stack designed for GPU-accelerated high performance computing (HPC) and machine learning workloads.
Singularity	A container platform targeted for high-performance computing (HPC) use case.
STT	Speech-to-Text (STT) refers to technologies or models that convert spoken language into written text, commonly used in voice recognition systems.
TensorFlow	TensorFlow is an open-source machine learning platform developed by Google, used for developing, training, and deploying machine learning models.
Ubuntu	A popular and generic Linux distribution widely used with machine learning and AI related applications.
VLLM	VLLM is an open-source Python library and inference engine designed for efficient and fast inference and serving of large language models.

YAML	YAML is a human-readable data serialization format often used for configuration files and data exchange between languages with different data structures.
YOLO	You Only Look Once (YOLO) is a real-time object detection algorithm in computer vision that predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities for objects in images in a single evaluation.

Executive Summary

One important part of the LUMI AI Factory Service Center's mission is to contribute to empowering Europe's AI ecosystem by developing and making available ready-to-use AI software solutions. Central to this effort is the provision of Containerized Workflows, which simplify the deployment of AI capabilities across various applications.

The Containerized Workflows consists of pre-built container images with tailored software, example data sets and pre-tested models to improve the accessibility of AI usage and development. The development of these workflows is linked with the broader LUMI AI Factory software ecosystem, which includes High-Performance Computing API (HPC-API) and Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) tools. Together, these elements will form an integrated environment where the development of different components supports each other. For instance, the container base images for various parts of the ecosystem, and the Containerized Workflows will share the same foundations.

The key objectives of developing the Containerized Workflows concept include delivering the first complete workflows early on. Additionally, new workflows will be continuously added throughout the lifetime of the LUMI AI Factory Service Center based on emerging opportunities and user needs. Initially, the focus is on developing workflows for Large Language Models (LLMs), including text processing workflows for tasks such as dataset curation, LLM fine-tuning, and LLM evaluation.

An important part of this development effort involves establishing processes, best practices, and tooling for creating these workflows. The concept of Containerized Workflows aims to include everything necessary to help new users get started quickly. It also provides a proven starting point for expert users to build upon for more specialized tasks. To support this, documentation with examples, openly licensed models tested with the workflows, and example datasets will be available directly within the environment.

This document provides an update on the status of the Containerized Workflows development and outlines the next steps in this ongoing effort.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	8
2. Background	9
2.1 AI Models, Software, and Use Cases	9
2.2 Current Use of Containers	10
2.3 Workflows, Containerized	11
3. Design and Implementation.....	13
3.1 Container Images	13
3.2 Workflow Files	14
3.3 Additional Artifacts	14
3.4 Installation and Directory Structure	15
3.5 Current Status	15
4. Workflow Catalog.....	16
4.1 LLM Text Processing	16
4.2 Vision-Language Batch Processing	17
4.3 YOLO Image Processing Workflow	18
4.4 Planned Future Workflows	19
5. Next Steps.....	20
6. References	21

1. Introduction

In recent years, the landscape of artificial intelligence has undergone significant advancements, with a growing number of AI tools and models becoming accessible and practical for a wide range of applications [1]. These developments have contributed to the democratization of AI, enabling researchers and practitioners across various domains to incorporate advanced technologies into their work [2]. As the use of AI continues to expand, the need for structured, scalable approaches to streamline deployment and integration has become increasingly evident.

To address these emerging needs and opportunities in AI adoption, the LUMI AI Factory Service Center is developing AI software solutions, including the Containerized Workflows concept, designed to streamline the execution of AI-related tasks. With Containerized Workflows concept, this is achieved by offering pre-prepared software, container images, datasets, models, and documentation as packages, tested to work properly together.

This effort is part of the larger LUMI AI Factory software ecosystem development, which includes developing tools and APIs such as the High-Performance Computing API (HPC-API), Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) tools, and AI model inference platforms (Aitta). These components collectively enhance the functionality and ease of use of AI software on LUMI and the future LUMI-AI supercomputers.

The Containerized Workflows work package is set to deliver a selection of functional workflows early on, with continuous updates based on user needs and technological advancements throughout the project. The initial focus is on developing workflows for Large Language Models (LLMs), including text processing, fine-tuning, and model evaluation tasks as well as workflows of different image processing tasks.

The development process for the Containerized Workflows involves establishing processes, best practices, and tools for creating and maintaining these workflows and the related artifacts. Key considerations include identifying use cases that address specific research needs, guiding the development of tailored workflows. The goal is to provide comprehensive workflow packages that enable both novice and expert users to quickly deploy and customize AI workflows, supported by detailed documentation, example datasets, and pre-tested models within the LUMI environment.

2. Background

The following sections provide an overview of key aspects underlying the demand for the Containerized Workflows as an approach for delivering AI capabilities on high-performance computing environments. These include the growing availability of open AI models and software tools [1], the adoption of container technologies in high-performance computing environments [3], and the opportunity for structured, reproducible workflows to accelerate the adoption of different AI tools in various domains and practical applications.

2.1 AI Models, Software, and Use Cases

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the availability of open AI models and AI-related tools. Examples include general-purpose language models such as LLaMA [4], Mistral [5], and Poro [6], domain-specific models for areas like protein structure prediction (AlphaFold [7]), as well as widely used software frameworks like PyTorch [8], Hugging Face Transformers [9] and optimized inference engines such as vLLM [10]. A large selection of resources is now freely accessible, enabling researchers and developers to build on these advanced capabilities without relying on proprietary systems, or coming up with custom solutions from scratch, for example when creating automated document analysis pipelines, training climate models, or developing computer vision systems for scientific imaging. While the availability of open models and tools offers great opportunities, it also introduces significant complexity, especially for those new to the field.

Many high-quality pre-trained models are openly available across domains such as language, vision, speech, and generative tasks. Examples include:

- **Natural Language Processing:** Models used in tasks like classification, summarization, and translation, for example automatically categorizing thousands of incoming customer support emails by topic, summarizing lengthy research reports for quick review, or translating technical documentation to multiple languages for international teams.
- **Computer Vision:** Models used in object detection, classification, and segmentation, for example identifying defects on a manufacturing line in real time, classifying satellite images to detect land use changes, or segmenting microscopic images for medical diagnosis.
- **Speech Recognition:** Models used for transcription and other audio-based tasks, for example converting meeting recordings into searchable transcripts, enabling voice-based commands in industrial equipment, or generating captions for live broadcasts.
- **Generative Models:** Models used for image generation from text prompts, audio synthesis, and video generation, for example creating photorealistic marketing visuals from a short description, synthesizing voiceovers in multiple languages for training videos, or producing short animations for educational content.

These models are often released under licenses that permit reuse and adaptation, and are typically accompanied by example code and documentation [11].

One important distinction to make is between open-weight models and fully open models. Open-weight models provide trained parameters for use in inference or fine-tuning but may withhold training data, code, or full methodology. Fully open models release these alongside the weights, enabling better

reproducibility, transparency, and more in-depth community-driven improvement [12]. While both types of models (and those in between) are useful, fully open models are often the most valuable for development purposes, yet they remain the least common.

In parallel with the growing availability of models, a wide range of open-source software tools has become central to AI development. Core machine learning frameworks such as PyTorch [8] and TensorFlow [13] provide the foundation for building and training models, while libraries like NumPy [14] and Pandas [15] support efficient data handling and preprocessing.

Despite these new opportunities, several challenges remain. Many of the available models and tools require significant computational resources, making them less accessible to individuals or smaller organizations. The learning curve can also be steep, particularly when moving from a source code repository with examples to a working solution.

The continued growth of openly available models and tools aligns well with the goals of the LUMI AI Factory Service Center. By leveraging these resources, the Containerized Workflows concept will improve both the accessibility and usability of AI technologies within the LUMI environment.

As the broader AI ecosystem evolves, integrating openly available models and software into well-structured workflows on LUMI, and later on LUMI-AI, will help researchers, developers, and users adopt new tools more easily and build on these state-of-the-art capabilities.

2.2 Current Use of Containers

The advancements in software containerization have transformed the landscape of software packaging and distribution practices. Initially, the main target for use of containerized software was in cloud environments, but later container use has been widely adopted almost everywhere, including high-performance computing environments, enabling greater flexibility, portability, and reproducibility also in scientific workflows [3].

Within the EuroHPC ecosystem, container technologies are an important piece for advancing Europe's supercomputing capabilities. LUMI, one of the most powerful pre-exascale supercomputers in Europe, exemplifies how containerization enhances computational efficiency and accessibility [16] [17] [18].

On LUMI, containerization is primarily provided through Singularity, a container runtime designed primarily for HPC environments [19]. Unlike other solutions (such as Docker), Singularity operates without need for super user rights, which aligns well with the security model of HPC systems [20]. This design choice reduces the potential risk of unauthorized access and typically allows containers to run with the same permissions as the user who launched them. Singularity is proven to work well with Slurm, LUMI's job scheduling system, making it a suitable solution for managing complex HPC software packages.

LUMI's hybrid CPU-GPU architecture, which includes AMD EPYC processors and AMD GPUs, offers unique opportunities and challenges for containerized workloads [21]. The system's specialized interconnect network is designed for high-speed data transfer and low-latency communication, requiring careful tuning and compatibility testing to achieve optimal performance [22]. Containers should be specifically prepared to leverage the advanced hardware features of LUMI, typically allowing for efficient utilization of GPU resources and reducing communication overhead.

Using AMD GPUs on LUMI presents challenges tied to the ROCm [23] software ecosystem. Unlike NVIDIA's CUDA [24], ROCm ecosystem is still less developed, with fewer pre-optimized containers and more potential compatibility issues with frameworks like PyTorch and TensorFlow [25]. Researchers may need to create custom container images for ROCm, which can be time-consuming.

Containerization can also introduce software licensing challenges, particularly for vendor-provided software, including key libraries, as licensing models may not account for containerized deployments, potentially leading to compliance issues. To address these challenges on LUMI, collaboration with software vendors and adherence to the system's licensing policies are necessary, sometimes employing creative solutions such as mounting the required libraries from the host system, which can decrease the portability of the containers.

The work invested in the software containerization so far provides a solid foundation for developing even more accessible containerized solutions for LUMI, LUMI-AI, and other systems. By leveraging the benefits of containerization and building upon it, we seek to establish a robust base that supports and enables an even wider range of users to take advantage of the emerging AI technologies.

2.3 Workflows, Containerized

Building on the foundation of containerization, Containerized Workflows aim to go a step further and streamline different computational tasks by enhancing both the ease of use and reproducibility. Containerized Workflows encapsulate applications and their entire software environment required for specific tasks, including software dependencies, libraries, and configuration settings, all provided in a convenient package. As with other containerized software available on LUMI, Containerized Workflows are also executed using Singularity via the Slurm job scheduler. In addition to containers, we provide example usage guides for specific tasks which supplement the whole Containerized Workflow.

Putting together a Containerized Workflow requires consideration of several aspects, including:

- Identifying Use Cases: Coming up with specific needs and opportunities for the workflows based on current research, trends, and user needs.
- Defining Requirements: Understanding the specific needs of specific workflows, including the software stack, data inputs, and computational resources required.
- Container Image Creation: Developing custom container images from scratch or extending existing ones to include all necessary components, optimized for LUMI's hybrid CPU-GPU architecture.
- Software Development: Creating software to be included with the workflow, such as working examples that utilize machine learning tools to accomplish specific real-world tasks, while serving also as a starting point for customization.
- Model and Dataset Selection: Selecting suitably licensed models and datasets to be used with the workflows.
- Testing and Validation: Ensuring compatibility, performance, and ease of use through testing.
- Documentation and User Guidance: Providing documentation and examples to facilitate ease of use and adoption by users.

Advantages of Containerized Workflows:

- **Portability:** Containers can be more easily moved and executed across similar environments, improving consistency and reproducibility of results.
- **Isolation:** Encapsulating the workflow within a container reduces the number of potential conflicts with the host system or other workflows.
- **Efficiency:** Containerized workflows can be designed to optimally utilize LUMI's resources, reducing overhead and improving performance.
- **Collaboration:** The workflow and container recipes can be developed collaboratively

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

The LUMI AI Factory Service Center is funded jointly by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking under Grant Agreement 101234208 and the Participating States FI, CZ, DK, EE, NO, PL.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3. Design and Implementation

Containerized Workflows are delivered by providing a set of container images, example workflow files, and documentation for specific tasks in using and developing AI models on LUMI and later LUMI-AI. Additionally, a set of pre-selected freely licensed foundation models and datasets are made available directly on the system to be used with these workflows, providing a useful, pre-tested starting point confirmed to function properly out of the box.

Ideally, users should be able to simply login to LUMI, read a bit of straightforward documentation, and based on that documentation, submit a job utilizing a Containerized Workflow for their own real-world task, without requiring expert-level prior exposure to the field.

While documentation is provided for using these workflows for specific use cases, the workflows are also useful for more advanced users as a starting point for creating custom workflows. Model training related workflows, container images and recipes will be designed to be compatible as part of LUMI AI Factory's MLOps based model development environment to be utilized by expert users.

The initially implemented workflows are designed to be practical for real-world use cases but focusing on simplicity for kick-starting the process of developing and managing the Containerized Workflows. The first workflows to be implemented include vLLM processing and visual processing workflows, detailed later in this document. These are planned to be followed by LLM fine-tuning and evaluation workflows.

3.1 Container Images

The development of Containerized Workflows involves creating and maintaining container images specifically tailored for use on compute nodes with the workflows. These container images are built on an Ubuntu Linux base image and AMD's ROCm software stack, compatible with the initially targeted hardware, which is the LUMI MI250x GPU partition.

While pre-existing container base images are available from various sources, we currently use custom builds. Custom images provide more complete control over the software stack, enabling us to keep all components up to date and optimized for the target hardware and workflows. This approach also simplifies maintenance process and aligns well with the project's objective of continuous improvement.

Significant prior work has already gone into developing container images for LUMI [16] [26]. With the Containerized Workflows concept, we aim to leverage this existing work as much as possible. However, since the final architecture of the upcoming LUMI-AI system has not yet been established, we are looking to produce the container images with architectural flexibility in mind. This effort is supported by the current LUMI system's visualization partition (LUMI-D), which features NVIDIA A40 GPUs. Using the LUMI-D partition enables us to test and develop workflows that are compatible with NVIDIA's software and hardware.

While LUMI's Singularity is used for running these images, we have established a separate image build environment based on Podman [27]. Compared to a Singularity-based build environment, the Podman approach uses the industry-standard image format, allows rapid iteration on readily available images, and integrates readily with common CI/CD pipelines and image management tools. This environment uses Dockerfiles [28], which are plain-text scripts that define all the steps, dependencies, and

configurations needed to create a container image. Our goal is to develop a continuous integration pipeline to automatically build and test the images against upstream updates.

Here is an example of images we currently build for the Containerized Workflows and how they stack on each other:

- Ubuntu-Rocm: A basic Ubuntu image with ROCm support, serving as the foundation for other images.
- Ubuntu-Rocm-Torch: Extends the base image by adding ROCm-compatible versions of PyTorch and related libraries. This image uses Python's virtual environment to manage dependencies effectively.
- Ubuntu-Rocm-Torch-FA: Builds on the Ubuntu-Rocm-Torch image by incorporating Flash Attention for ROCm, enhancing performance for specific AI tasks.
- Ubuntu-Rocm-Torch-FA-vLLM: Further extends the functionality by including vLLM, providing additional capabilities for language model inference.

3.2 Workflow Files

The workflow programs implement the core functionality of each workflow by making use of various AI-related software libraries. They are developed in collaboration with contributing partner organizations (currently CSC, IT4I and Sigma2) to ensure broad coverage of use cases by bringing expertise from each organization. The programs are primarily written in Python, which is the dominant programming language in the AI field.

All workflow program files and related artifacts, such as batch scripts, configuration files, and documentation, are tracked in a Git version control repository. This enables clear change tracking, facilitates smooth collaboration, and contributes to the robustness and maintainability of the Containerized Workflows ecosystem. In addition to the workflow files, the recipes used to build the container images are also tracked in Git version control repositories as a part of the overall development process.

3.3 Additional Artifacts

Currently, the following AI models have been made directly available on LUMI for use with the implemented workflows:

- Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct
- Llama-Propo-2-70B-Instruct
- Mistral-Small-3.1-24B-Instruct-2503
- Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct-2506
- Qwen2.5-VL-3B-Instruct
- Qwen2.5-VL-72B-Instruct
- Qwen2.5-VL-7B-Instruct
- Ultralytics YOLO11

We provide small example datasets with the existing workflows and are currently evaluating additional datasets for their suitability to be made directly available on LUMI. These are expected to be added in

near future. Bigger datasets will become increasingly important as we begin implementing the various fine-tuning and evaluation workflows. These needs will also be addressed by the LUMI AI Factory's Work Package WP5, which specifically focuses on data access and management, including deliverable D5.2 - Dataset as a Service.

3.4 Installation and Directory Structure

The initial installation of the first Containerized Workflows has been completed on LUMI. To support the management of container images and related files, a dedicated, non-expiring LUMI project has been created. This project is used to manage artifacts deployed on the system, including file ownership and access permissions for modifying container images and associated resources. A similar approach is used to manage the official LUST-provided LUMI software stack and other local installations, such as those in `/appl/local/csc`.

On the system side, the project is linked to a specific group, and the necessary directories have been created with appropriate access controls. These directories are made available to users through a designated path, enabling straightforward access and efficient permissions management across the environment.

The Containerized Workflow associated files are stored under directory path `/appl/local/laifs` on LUMI. To ensure high availability and data redundancy, this directory will be replicated across LUMI's four Lustre file systems. This setup provides resilience, ensuring that workflows and related files remain accessible even in the event of a file system failure. The same approach is used with the existing official LUMI software stack.

The structure below illustrates how the directories supporting the Containerized Workflows and related components have been organized on LUMI.

```
/appl/local/laifs
  /containers
    / laifs-lumi-multi-20250728_103251.sif (the image itself)
    / laifs-lumi-multi-20250728_103251.md (image documentation)
  /models
    /Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct-2506 (model directories)
    [...]
  /workflows
    /vllm-text-processing (directory for a workflow)
    /examples (examples directory)
    /README.md (workflow documentation)
    [...]
  /datasets
```

3.5 Current Status

The initial workflows described in the next chapter (LLM Text Processing, Vision-Language Batch Processing, and YOLO Image Processing) have been made available to all LUMI users, with full examples and detailed instructions accessible directly on LUMI. Overview documentation for the workflows is available under the official LUMI user documentation [29].

4. Workflow Catalog

This chapter lists the currently implemented workflows and introduces few new workflows planned to be implemented in future.

4.1 LLM Text Processing

Status: Initial implementation has been completed, and the workflow is available for LUMI user.

Description:

The LLM Text Processing workflow is designed to facilitate efficient text processing using Large Language Models (LLMs). This workflow is implemented as a ready-to-go container image and recipe, specifically tailored for tasks such as dataset curation. It leverages the vLLM library to process input files based on user-provided instructions and generate corresponding output files. The vLLM engine implements optimized tensor-parallel batched inference for high performance, while the workflow as a whole provides a tested, ready-to-use setup that allows users to get started quickly without extensive configuration or troubleshooting.

Key Features:

- **Input and Output Handling:** The workflow processes files in a specified input directory and generates output files in a designated output directory. Each input file is processed according to the given instructions, with the output being either a single file or one output file per input file.
- **Task Configuration:** The workflow allows for command-line or YAML configuration file inputs, providing flexibility in defining the processing tasks. Users can specify the model to be used, input and output file paths, and instructions for processing.
- **Custom Scripts and Models:** Users can customize the workflow script and select from a set of ready-to-go models that have been tested to work efficiently within the workflow.
- **Scalability:** The processing speed scales well with the number of input files. Optimal performance is achieved with a larger number of input files, leveraging the efficiency of batched processing used in vLLM.

Planned Improvements:

- Allow multi-step processing without reloading the language model.

Usage overview:

To utilize the LLM Text Processing workflow, users can begin by copying one of the provided example directories from the workflow's examples folder into their own working directory. The examples serve as templates and include all necessary files and configurations to run a text processing job.

Once the example directory is copied, users can submit the job to the computing cluster using a batch script included in the directory. This script requires users to specify their project account to allocate the necessary resources for job execution.

During job execution, users can monitor the progress and status using standard Slurm commands. This allows for real-time tracking of the job's output and overall progress once it has started.

Upon completion of the job, the workflow generates output files in the specified output directory. These files contain the processed results based on the input files and instructions provided.

For detailed specific examples, users can refer to the example README files located within the workflow example directories. These files provide comprehensive instructions, sample task configurations in YAML format, and example instruction files that guide users through setting up and customizing their text processing tasks.

4.2 Vision-Language Batch Processing

Status: Initial implementation has been completed, and the workflow is available for LUMI user.

Description: The Vision-Language Batch Processing workflow is designed to facilitate efficient image processing, such as object detection, classification, segmentation, motion-tracking, using vision-language models. This workflow leverages container and with Transformers library to process input images based on user-provided instructions and generate corresponding output files with textual answers.

Key Features:

- **Input and Output Handling:** The workflow processes images in a specified input directory and generates output text files in a designated output directory. Each input image is processed according to the given instructions, with the output being one text file per input image.
- **Task Configuration:** The workflow uses a YAML configuration file to define the processing tasks. Users can specify the model to be used, input and output file paths, and instructions for processing.
- **Custom Scripts and Models:** Users can customize the workflow script and select from a set of ready-to-go models that have been tested to work properly within the workflow.
- **Scalability:** The processing speed scales well with the number of input images, based the efficiency of batched processing provided in the Transformers library.

Planned Improvements:

- Enable using quantized models like AWQ to improve loading times and overall performance.
- Conduct an additional code review to ensure the quality and maintainability of the workflow.

Usage Overview: To utilize the Hugging Face Vision-Language Batch Processing workflow, users can begin by submitting the provided SLURM script to launch a demo job on LUMI. The script requests GPU resources and sets sensible defaults for interactive testing.

Once the job is submitted, the container execution begins, and the vision-language pipeline is executed. The pipeline reads a YAML task specification, loads a Qwen2.5 vision-language model, loops over the input images, asks the prompt, and stores the model's answer in the corresponding output text files.

Users can create their own tasks by preparing input images, writing a prompt, creating a task.yaml file that points to the inputs, outputs, and instructions, and running the job by adapting the last line of the run_container.sh script to point to their YAML and re-submitting with sbatch.

For detailed specific examples, users can refer to the example README files located within the workflow example directories. These files provide comprehensive instructions, sample task configurations in YAML format, and example instruction files that guide users through setting up and customizing their image processing tasks.

4.3 YOLO Image Processing Workflow

Status: Initial implementation has been completed, and the workflow is available for LUMI user.

Description: The YOLO Image Processing Workflow is designed to facilitate efficient image processing using YOLO (You Only Look Once) models. This workflow is implemented as a ready-to-go container image and a workflow recipe, suited for tasks such as object classification. It processes input image files and generates corresponding output files with class predictions in a human-readable format.

Key Features:

- **Input and Output Handling:** The workflow processes images in a specified input directory and generates output text files in a designated output directory with one text file per input image.
- **Task Configuration:** The workflow uses a YAML configuration file to define the processing tasks. Users can specify the model directory and file, input and output file paths.
- **Scalability:** The processing speed scales well with the number of input images, leveraging the efficiency of batched processing.

Planned Improvements:

- None at the moment

Usage Overview: To utilize the YOLO Image Processing Workflow, users can begin by copying one of the provided example directories from the workflow's examples folder into their own working directory. The examples serve as templates and include all necessary files and configurations to run an image processing job.

Once the example directory is copied, users can submit the job to the computing cluster using a batch script included in the directory. This script requires users to specify their project account to allocate the necessary resources for job execution.

During job execution, users can monitor the progress and status using standard Slurm commands. This allows for real-time tracking of the job's output and overall progress once it has started.

Upon completion of the job, the workflow generates output text files in the specified output directory. These files contain the class predictions based on the input images.

For detailed specific examples, users can refer to the example README files located within the workflow example directories. These files provide comprehensive instructions, sample task configurations in YAML format, and example instruction files that guide users through setting up and customizing their image processing tasks.

4.4 Planned Future Workflows

Looking forward to expanding the selection of available workflows, we are considering introducing several new workflows. These upcoming workflows should be beneficial for addressing several opportunities in research and other use cases. Below is our current list of planned and ones in idea stage.

LLM Fine-tuning

Status: Planned to be implemented

Description: This workflow will provide ready-to-go recipes and container images for fine-tuning pre-trained and instruction-tuned foundation models using custom datasets. The workflow will include a set of tested models readily available on LUMI, container images, example datasets, and example job files for launching training jobs. This will enable users to adapt existing models to specific tasks or domains, improving their performance and relevance. The workflow will support a variety of pre-trained models and model architectures.

LLM Evaluation

Status: Planned to be implemented

Description: This workflow will offer a containerized solution for running standard LLM evaluation benchmarks, such as GPQA (Graduate-Level Google-Proof Q&A) and MMLU (Massive Multitask Language Understanding). Standard benchmarks are central for assessing the performance and capabilities of language models, providing insights into model strengths and weaknesses.

Speech to Text

Status: Under consideration

Description: This workflow will enable transcribing audio files to text using Speech-to-Text (STT) models. This capability can be useful multiple research and application areas. The workflow will include pre-trained models, container images, and example audio files to demonstrate the transcription process.

Workflow Frameworks

Status: Under consideration

Description: We are evaluating the usefulness of providing workflows enabling the use of workflow engines such as [Nextflow](#), [OpenWDL](#), [Snakemake](#) and [StreamFlow](#).

5. Next Steps

The next phase of development for the Containerized Workflows includes increasing the coverage of the workflows for different tasks, enhancing the functionality, accessibility, and user experience of the existing workflows, and streamlining the Containerized Workflows development process as well as finalizing a process for user support requests related to the workflows.

Building on the initial set of provided workflows of LLM Text Processing, Vision-Language Batch Processing, and YOLO Image Processing Workflows, we will proceed to expand the catalog of available workflows. The next phase is planned to include the development of workflows for LLM fine-tuning and LLM benchmark evaluation. Additionally, we will explore workflows for audio processing, such as Speech-to-Text. We will also continue tracking the software and AI model landscape to identify opportunities for integrating new technologies and tools to ensure that the Containerized Workflows concept remain up-to-date and effectively meet the needs of the user community.

Maintaining the created workflows is crucial. This involves regularly updating the containers images to the latest software versions to improve performance, fix bugs, and maintain the security of the software components. Additionally, system upgrades on LUMI may break compatibility with the workflows, which may require additional work to ensure continuous operation and smooth user experience. We aim to provide a stable and efficient environment for users to continuously accomplish their AI-related tasks.

Continuous improvement of the development processes is needed for achieving high standards for the Containerized Workflows concept. This involves adopting best practices in software development, containerization, and efficient collaboration between the contributing partner organizations. By refining the processes, we aim to ensure the workflows are robust, reliable, and beneficial to the users. Code reviews, automated testing, and CI/CD pipelines are planned to be implemented to streamline the development process.

Additionally, we are looking to establish clear channels for user communication and feedback to enable us to gather insights and address any issues the users may face promptly. We are looking to provide regular updates to keep the users informed about improvements and upcoming workflows.

In conclusion, the groundwork for the Containerized Workflows has been successfully laid with the initial set of workflows and supporting infrastructure now available on LUMI. This foundation enables us to move forward with expanding functionality, improving usability and improving the development process. Moving forward, our focus is on collaboration, maintainability, and scalability of the concept. Through ongoing technical refinement and user engagement, we strive to make sure that the Containerized Workflows concept becomes a sustainable and impactful toolset for AI development and research on LUMI, and at later stage, on LUMI-AI.

6. References

- [1] "Recent Trends in Artificial Intelligence Technology: A Scoping Review [arXiv:2305.04532v3]," 2023.
- [2] "Exploring the Latest Trends in AI Technologies: A Study on Current State, Application and Individual Impacts [10.4236/jcc.2024.128002]," 2024.
- [3] "Containerisation for High Performance Computing Systems: Survey and Prospects [arXiv:2212.08717]," 2022.
- [4] "Huggingface Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct Model Card," [Online]. Available: <https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct>.
- [5] "Huggingface Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct-2506 Model Card," [Online]. Available: <https://huggingface.co/mistralai/Mistral-Small-3.2-24B-Instruct-2506>.
- [6] "Huggingface Poro-34B-chat Model Card," [Online]. Available: <https://huggingface.co/LumiOpen/Poro-34B-chat>.
- [7] "AlphaFold," [Online]. Available: <https://deepmind.google/science/alphafold/>.
- [8] "Pytorch," [Online]. Available: <https://pytorch.org>.
- [9] "Huggingface Transformers," [Online]. Available: <https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/en/index>.
- [10] "vLLM," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.vllm.ai/en/latest/>.
- [11] "An Empirical Study of Pre-Trained Model Reuse in the Hugging Face Deep Learning Model Registry [arXiv:2303.02552]," 2023.
- [12] "Comprehensive Analysis of Transparency and Accessibility of ChatGPT, DeepSeek, and other SoTA Large Language Models [arXiv:2502.18505v1]," 2025.
- [13] "Tensorflow," [Online]. Available: <https://www.tensorflow.org>.
- [14] "Numpy," [Online]. Available: <https://numpy.org/>.
- [15] "Pandas," [Online]. Available: <https://pandas.pydata.org>.
- [16] "LUMI Documentation, Container jobs," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/runjobs/scheduled-jobs/container-jobs/>.

- [17] "LUMI EasyBuild containers," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Lumi-supercomputer/LUMI-EasyBuild-containers>.
- [18] "Enabling Message Passing Interface Containers on the LUMI Supercomputer [arXiv:2407.19928]," 2024.
- [19] "LUMI Documentation - Singularity," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/software/containers/singularity/>.
- [20] "Singularity Documentation - Security in Singularity," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.sylabs.io/guides/3.5/user-guide/security.html>.
- [21] "LUMI Documentation, GPU nodes - LUMI-G," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/hardware/lumig/>.
- [22] "LUMI Documentation, Network and interconnect," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/hardware/network/>.
- [23] "Radeon Open Compute Documentation," [Online]. Available: <https://rocm.docs.amd.com/en/latest/>.
- [24] "NVidia Cuda," [Online]. Available: <https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda-toolkit>.
- [25] "A Systematic Literature Review on Graphics Processing Unit Accelerated Realm of High-Performance Computing [10.47941/ijce.1813]," [Online].
- [26] "LUMI-container Image Docker Recipes," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/sfantao/LUMI-containers/tree/main/RecipesDocker>.
- [27] "Podman," [Online]. Available: <https://podman.io/>.
- [28] "Docker documentation, Dockerfile," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.docker.com/reference/dockerfile/>.
- [29] "LUMI User Documentation/LUMI AI Factory," [Online]. Available: <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/software/local/lumi-aif>.
- [30] "Is Open Source the Future of AI? A Data-Driven Approach. [arXiv:2501.16403v1]," 2025.
- [31] "How Far Behind Are Open Models?," [Online]. Available: <https://epoch.ai/blog/open-models-report>.

